

SolarPACES 2024, 30th International Conference on Concentrating Solar Power, Thermal, and Chemical Energy Systems

Receivers and Heat Transfer Media and Transport: Point Focus Systems

<https://doi.org/10.52825/xxxx.....> DOI placeholder (WILL BE FILLED IN BY TIB Open Publishing)

© Authors. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Published: (WILL BE FILLED IN BY TIB Open Publishing)

Inverse Heat Transfer Analysis for Estimating Heat Flux in Solar Tower Receivers

Vahid Safari ¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7834-8240>,

Antonio Acosta-Iborra ¹ [https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3848-](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3848-4974)

4974

¹ Department of Thermal and Fluids Engineering, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. Avda. de la Universidad 30, Leganés 28911, Madrid (Spain)

* Correspondence: Vahid Safari, vsafari@ing.uc3m.es

Abstract. Solar power tower plants are utilized to harness solar radiation for large-scale electricity generation. The concentrated solar radiation is absorbed by the central receiver to heat a transfer fluid, which is typically a mixture of 40% sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) and 60% potassium nitrate (KNO_3). Extreme conditions, including high temperatures and variable heat flux, are experienced by these central receivers, necessitating precise thermal measurements to optimize energy production and maintain efficiency. In this paper, an in-house code based on an inverse analysis technique is developed to determine the absorbed heat flux on the surface of the concentrated solar power (CSP) receiver tube, using surface temperature measurements as input. It is found that a single temperature measurement from the frontal part of the tube ($0 \leq \theta < 90^\circ$) is sufficient for the estimation of the absorbed flux within an acceptable deviation. Additionally, noise is incorporated into the input temperature data to evaluate the reliability of the code under fluctuating conditions typical of real-world applications. The effectiveness of the code in this scenario is demonstrated, reinforcing its potential for practical applications.

Keywords: Inverse heat conduction problem, Solar tower receivers, Heat flux estimation

1. Introduction

Accurately determining the absorbed heat flux on receiver tube surfaces is crucial for optimizing the performance of concentrating solar power systems [1]. While direct heat flux measurements are ideal, they pose significant challenges in tubular receiver systems [2]. Consequently, computational methods, particularly inverse heat conduction analysis, have emerged as valuable tools for estimating heat flux profiles [3,4]. The strength of inverse analysis lies in its ability to estimate parameters that are difficult or impossible to measure directly, making it particularly valuable for characterizing heat transfer phenomena in complex systems like tubular receivers. Unlike traditional direct heat conduction problems, where boundary heat fluxes are known and temperature distributions are calculated, inverse heat conduction analysis utilizes surface temperature measurements to determine unknown boundary conditions. This iterative process involves refining model parameters until the predicted temperatures closely match the input observed data.

2. Numerical model

The numerical model utilized in this study is based on the inverse method, which comprises several key components [5]. Initially, the direct problem involves solving the heat conduction equation with known parameters to predict temperature distributions. In contrast, the inverse problem aims to infer unknown parameters, such as heat flux, from measured temperature data. A critical component of the inverse analysis is sensitivity analysis [6], which assesses how variations in parameters influence the output, thereby guiding the optimization process. To enhance the accuracy of the model, the conjugate gradient method [7] is frequently employed due to its efficiency in minimizing discrepancies between predicted and observed data through iterative adjustments. An in-house MATLAB code was developed using the inverse analysis method to estimate the heat flux of a solar tower receiver tube based on temperature measurements taken at various positions. The benchmark data, which served as input for the code, consisted of temperature readings at different circumferential locations obtained from Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations conducted using ANSYS Fluent.

2.1. Direct problem

A transient 2D numerical model was developed, and for simplicity, heat transfer along the flow was not included. The heat exchange between the molten salt and the pipe wall was assessed using Petukhov's correlation [8]. Consequently, heat transfer by conduction occurs in the radial and circumferential directions along the pipe, following the heat diffusion equation:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial t} = k \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial \theta^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where T is the wall temperature, ρ is the wall density, C_p is the specific heat of the wall, and k is the thermal conductivity of the wall. The boundary and initial conditions for the direct problem are defined as follows:

$$-k \frac{\partial T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial r} = h_i (T_s - T(r, \theta, t)), \quad \text{at } r = r_i \quad (2)$$

$$-k \frac{\partial T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial r} = h_{\text{conv+rad}}(\theta, t) (T(r, \theta, t) - T_\infty) - q_{\text{inc}}(\theta, t), \quad \text{at } r = r_o \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial T(r, \theta, t)}{\partial \theta} = 0, \quad \text{at } \theta = 0, \pi \quad (4)$$

$$T(r, \theta, t) = T_{\text{ini}}, \quad \text{for } t = 0 \quad (5)$$

Where r_i and r_o are the inner and outer radii of the pipe. T_s and T_∞ denote the temperatures of the molten salt and the environment. h_i refers to the convective heat transfer from the molten salt to the pipe's inner wall, while $h_{\text{conv+rad}}$ describes the combined convective and radiative heat transfer from the pipe's outer surface to the atmosphere. For the numerical CFD simulation using ANSYS Fluent, q_{inc} was assumed to follow a cosine function, while the area not exposed to the sun received no heat flux:

$$q_{\text{inc}} = \begin{cases} q_{\text{inc}}(t) \cdot \text{Cos}(\theta) & , 0 \leq \theta < 90^\circ \\ 0 & , 90^\circ \leq \theta \leq 180^\circ \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

2.2. Inverse problem

For solving the inverse heat conduction problem, the conjugate gradient method [7] was employed, accompanied by an adjoint problem for parameter estimation. This formulation integrates the direct problem outlined in the previous section, along with the sensitivity problem [6], the adjoint problem [9], and the gradient equations.

To solve the inverse problem, the unknown function can be parameterized as follows:

$$q_{\text{inc}} = P \times C(\theta, t) \quad (7)$$

In which P is the unknown parameter and $C(\theta, t)$ is a trial function. The objective of the inverse problem is to ascertain the unknown parameter P using measurements of wall temperature at $r = r_o$ and various circumferential locations, represented as $Y_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}$. Thus, solving the inverse problem involves minimizing the following functional:

$$J[P] = \sum_{m=1}^{M_n} \int_{t=0}^{t_f} \left(T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m} - Y_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m} \right)^2 dt \quad (8)$$

Here, M_n represents the total number of temperature measurement points, t_f denotes the total time, and $T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}$ is the numerical solution at the measurement positions, derived from the direct problem using an estimated heat flux q_{inc}^k that was previously calculated.

2.3. Conjugate gradient method

The process for identifying the unknown parameter P involves minimizing the functional $J[P]$ through the iterative use of the conjugate gradient method. At the k th iteration, P is estimated according to the specified expression:

$$P^{k+1} = P^k - \beta^k d^k \quad (9)$$

Where β^k represents the step size for the search and d^k indicates the descent direction, which can be calculated through the following expression:

$$d^k = J'[P^k] + \gamma^k d^{k-1} \quad (10)$$

In which $J'[P]$ is the gradient of equation (8) obtained through the adjoint method, which involves multiplying equation (1) by a Lagrange multiplier and integrating the resulting expression over both space and time. γ^k is the conjugation coefficient, calculated using the following expression:

$$\gamma^k = \frac{(J'[P^k])^2}{(J'[P^{k-1}])^2}, \quad \gamma^0 = 0 \quad (11)$$

The step size β^k is also determined by minimizing the functional $J[P^{k+1}]$ in relation to β^k :

$$\beta^k = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^{M_n} \int_{t=0}^{t_f} \left[(T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}(P^k) - Y_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}) \Delta T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}(d^k) \right] dt}{\sum_{m=1}^{M_n} \int_{t=0}^{t_f} \left[\Delta T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}(d^k) \right]^2 dt} \quad (12)$$

Where $T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}(P^k)$ represents the result of the direct problem at the specified measurement locations of $\theta = \theta_m$ based on the estimated P^k and $\Delta T_{r=r_o, \theta=\theta_m}(d^k)$ denotes the solution of the sensitivity problem at $\theta = \theta_m$ utilizing $\Delta P = d^k$.

2.4. Stop criteria

The stopping criterion is established based on the discrepancy principle, which stipulates that the procedure is terminated when the value of the functional becomes less than the variance of the measurement errors.

$$J[P] < M_n \sigma^2 t_f \quad (13)$$

Where M_n represents the total number of temperature measurement points, and σ denotes the standard deviation of the measurement errors.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Ansys simulation result

Figure 1 illustrates the heat flux (a), and temperature (b) contours derived from the 3D ANSYS simulation. The generated heat flux is a result of the aiming strategy for the equatorial position ($k = 3$) during the spring equinox, with a Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) value of $900 \text{ W} / \text{m}^2$. Molten salt, composed of 40% NaNO_3 and 60% KNO_3 [10], flows through the receiver tube at an inlet temperature of 290°C and an inlet mass flow rate of $2.842 \text{ kg} / \text{s}$. The resulted temperature profile will be used as input data for the inverse analysis code, while the heat flux curve will serve to validate the accuracy of the predicted heat flux produced by the inverse analysis. Given that the code operates in a two-dimensional framework, temperature and heat flux data are obtained from a single cross-section at $Z=5.5\text{m}$ (as indicated by the curves within the figures).

Figure 1. Heat flux (a), and temperature (b) contours derived from the 3D ANSYS simulation

Figure 2 (a) presents the 2D cross-section of the tube, including the boundary conditions utilized in the inverse analysis code. Only half of the tube is simulated due to the symmetry inherent in the model. To assess the independence of the generated grid, four different mesh resolutions were tested. It was determined that a grid comprising 9 elements in the radial direction and 54 elements in the circumferential direction provided the best choices, balancing acceptable computational cost and error (Figure 2 (b)).

Figure 2. 2D cross-section of the simulated domain (a) and results of the independence test (b) used in the inverse analysis code

Figure 3 (a) displays the predicted heat flux from the inverse analysis code, which utilizes single-point temperature data from the outer surface of the tube as input. The input temperature angle varies from 10° to 110° . As shown, in the frontal section of the tube ($0 \leq \theta < 90^\circ$), the optimal input temperature angle is identified as 60° , resulting in the least deviation between the predicted heat flux and the results obtained from ANSYS, as illustrated in Figure 2 (b). Angles below 60° typically lead to an underestimation of the heat flux, while angles above 60° are associated with an overestimation. In the rear section of the tube ($90^\circ \leq \theta \leq 180^\circ$), it is evident that angles exceeding

90° contribute to significantly greater deviations. Specifically, using angles of 90° and 110° results in discrepancies of 16.19% and 93.95%, respectively, compared to the reference heat flux value obtained from ANSYS.

Figure 3. Predicted heat flux (a) and resulting deviation error (b) from the inverse analysis code

In real-world applications, obtaining perfectly smooth data without fluctuations is nearly impossible. To assess the effectiveness of the developed inverse analysis code, a transient stream of temperature data was augmented with white noise characterized by standard deviations of ± 2 , ± 4 , and ± 6 (Figure 4(a)). White noise is defined as a random signal with a constant power spectral density, resulting in unpredictable variations. As illustrated in Figure 4(b), the predicted heat flux shows only minor deviations and increases slightly with higher standard deviations. These findings highlight the robustness and reliability of the developed code in effectively handling noisy data, thereby confirming its suitability for practical applications.

Figure 4. Introduced noisy temperature data (a) with the resulting heat flux prediction (b) from the inverse analysis code

4. Conclusion

In this study, a transient 2D numerical code based on the inverse analysis method was developed to estimate the heat flux in solar tower receivers effectively. The results demonstrate that a single temperature measurement from the frontal part of the receiver tube can yield accurate heat flux estimations, with optimal performance observed at a temperature angle of 60°. In contrast, predictions in the rear part of the tube showed significant deviations, particularly with angles exceeding 90°, which contributed to overestimation of heat flux. The robustness of the code was further validated by incorporating noise into the temperature data, revealing that predictions remained reliable despite fluctuations. This capability underscores the method's practical applicability in real-world scenarios where data imperfections are common.

Data availability statement

Data will be made available upon request.

Author contributions

Vahid Safari: Methodology, Validation, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. María Fernandez-Torrijos: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. Antonio Acosta-Iborra: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. Celia Sobrino: Supervision, Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Funding

This work was funded by the European Union (HORIZON MSCA Doctoral Network, Project number 101072537).

References

- [1] M. Fernández-Torrijos, C. Sobrino, J.A. Almendros-Ibáñez, C. Marugán-Cruz, D. Santana, Inverse heat problem of determining unknown surface heat flux in a molten salt loop, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 139 (2019) 503–516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2019.05.002>.
- [2] M. Fernández-Torrijos, C. Sobrino, C. Marugán-Cruz, D. Santana, Experimental and numerical study of the heat transfer process during the startup of molten salt tower receivers, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 178 (2020) 115528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2020.115528>.
- [3] N. Perakis, O.J. Haidn, Inverse heat transfer method applied to capacitively cooled rocket thrust chambers, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 131 (2019) 150–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IJHEATMASSTRANSFER.2018.11.048>.
- [4] J. Taler, P. Duda, B. Weglowski, W. Zima, S. Gradziel, T. Sobota, D. Taler, Identification

- of local heat flux to membrane water-walls in steam boilers, *Fuel*. 88 (2009) 305–311. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUEL.2008.08.011>.
- [5] K.A. Woodbury, H. Najafi, F. Monte, J. V. Beck, *Inverse Heat Conduction*, *Inverse Heat Conduct.* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119840220>.
- [6] O.M. Alifanov, *Inverse Heat Transfer Problems*, (1994). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-76436-3>.
- [7] T. Lu, B. Liu, P.X. Jiang, Y.W. Zhang, H. Li, A two-dimensional inverse heat conduction problem in estimating the fluid temperature in a pipeline, *Appl. Therm. Eng.* 30 (2010) 1574–1579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2010.03.011>.
- [8] B.S. Petukhov, *Heat Transfer and Friction in Turbulent Pipe Flow with Variable Physical Properties*, *Adv. Heat Transf.* 6 (1970) 503–564. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2717\(08\)70153-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2717(08)70153-9).
- [9] J. Su, A.J. Silva Neto, Two-dimensional inverse heat conduction problem of source strength estimation in cylindrical rods, *Appl. Math. Model.* 25 (2001) 861–872. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0307-904X\(01\)00018-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0307-904X(01)00018-X).
- [10] A.B. ZAVOICO, *Solar Power Tower Design Basis Document, Revision 0, Tech. Rep. SAND2001-2100*. (2001) 148. <https://doi.org/10.2172/786629>.